

Smart Helmet with Accident Detection and Alert System

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Abstract

Road accidents involving two-wheeler riders remain a serious public safety concern in India, with over 1.5 lakh fatalities reported annually according to Ministry of Road Transport and Highways data. A major share of these accidents happen due to riders not wearing helmets properly, drunk driving, and the delay in getting emergency help after an accident occurs. To address these problems, this paper presents the design and implementation of a Smart Helmet integrated with accident detection and real-time alert functionality. The system uses an MPU6050 six-axis IMU for detecting sudden impact events, a NEO-6M GPS module for location tracking, an MQ-3 gas sensor for alcohol detection, and an ESP8266 microcontroller as the main processing unit. When an accident is detected based on a dual-threshold algorithm using accelerometer and gyroscope readings, the system sends an emergency alert via a Telegram Bot along with the rider's GPS location as a clickable Google Maps link. Communication is handled entirely over Wi-Fi using the Telegram Bot API, which was chosen over GSM after evaluating both options during the design phase. The system also uses a hybrid energy harvesting approach combining a solar panel and piezoelectric transducers to reduce battery dependency. The prototype was tested under various controlled conditions and showed an average accident detection response time of about 1.3 seconds and Telegram alert delivery within 3 to 5 seconds. The total component cost is approximately Rs. 1,840, making it a practical and affordable solution.

Keywords — Smart Helmet, Accident Detection, MPU6050, GPS NEO-6M, Telegram Bot, ESP8266, MQ-3 Alcohol Sensor, Solar Energy Harvesting, Piezoelectric, IoT, Road Safety.

I. Introduction

India has one of the highest numbers of road accident deaths in the world. Two-wheeler riders account for a large portion of these fatalities, and the main reasons are non-use of helmets, drunk driving, and the unavailability of quick emergency help. Traditional helmets are purely passive protective devices – they protect the head during impact but do nothing else. There is no automatic way for the helmet to detect whether an accident has happened or to send help.

With the availability of low-cost microcontrollers like the ESP8266 and easy-to-use communication platforms like Telegram, it has become possible to build practical smart helmet systems that were not feasible before. Sensors like the MPU6050 IMU and MQ-3 gas sensor are affordable and well-supported, which makes integrating them into a helmet a realistic project.

This project presents a smart helmet system that can detect accident events using motion analysis, identify alcohol usage through breath sensing, track the rider's location via GPS, and send an emergency alert to a pre-registered contact through the Telegram messaging platform – all in real-time and without any recurring cost. The system is powered by a Li-ion battery supplemented by solar and piezoelectric energy harvesting, which improves battery life during daytime use.

II. Literature Review

Several researchers have worked on smart helmet systems over the past decade. Arun et al. [1] proposed an early smart helmet using Arduino, GSM, and GPS, where an accelerometer detected impact and an SMS was sent. Limitations included GSM cost and no alcohol detection. Rajeswari et al. [2] used Raspberry Pi with GSM for a more elaborate system but this was bulky and expensive. Nithya and Malathi [3] improved accident detection by using the MPU6050 six-axis IMU instead of a single vibration sensor.

Suresh et al. [4] added MQ-3 alcohol detection alongside an accelerometer for a more comprehensive approach, though GPS was missing. Patel et al. [5] demonstrated piezoelectric energy harvesting from helmet vibrations as a concept. Kumar and Sharma [6] showed that the ESP8266 can reliably use the Telegram Bot API for IoT alerts, though not applied to helmets. Divya et al. [7] first applied Telegram-based alerting to a smart helmet using ESP8266, MPU6050, and GPS but without energy harvesting or alcohol detection.

Yadav et al. [8] demonstrated solar panel integration in a two-wheeler IoT device. Priya et al. [9] combined helmet compliance, alcohol detection, and accident sensing in one prototype using GSM but without GPS. Mehta et al. [10] studied hybrid solar-piezoelectric harvesting and showed 35 to 45 percent power supplement is achievable in wearable devices.

Based on this review, the proposed system combines all key features – accident detection, GPS alerting, alcohol sensing, Telegram communication, and hybrid energy harvesting – into one affordable prototype addressing gaps in existing work.

III. Problem Statement

Two-wheeler riders in India face a high risk of serious injury in road accidents due to: (a) not wearing a helmet properly, (b) drunk driving, and (c) delayed emergency response. Existing research prototypes generally suffer from high GSM communication costs, no GPS integration, or absence of energy harvesting. There is a need for a smart helmet that is low-cost, integrates multiple safety features, and uses internet-based communication without ongoing SIM expenses.

IV. Proposed Methodology

The proposed system follows a sensor-processor-communication architecture where the ESP8266 microcontroller acts as the central unit. It reads data from the MPU6050, MQ-3, and GPS module, applies decision logic, and sends alerts through the Telegram Bot API over Wi-Fi when required.

On power-up, the ESP8266 initializes all sensors and connects to Wi-Fi. The GPS module starts acquiring satellite signals and the system waits for a valid fix before enabling monitoring. The main loop continuously reads sensor data. If MQ-3 detects alcohol above the threshold, an alert is sent. If MPU6050 detects a sudden impact crossing both thresholds, a 30-second countdown begins. If normal motion is not detected within this window, a Telegram alert with the GPS location link is sent to the emergency contact.

The decision to use Telegram Bot instead of GSM was made after testing both approaches. Telegram delivered messages in 3 to 5 seconds vs. 15 to 40 seconds for GSM SMS. It also allows a clickable Google Maps link instead of plain text coordinates. Since ESP8266 has built-in Wi-Fi, no additional hardware was needed, and the GSM module was removed from the final design.

V. Hardware Components Description

A. ESP8266 Microcontroller

The ESP8266 features a dual-core processor at up to 240 MHz, 520 KB SRAM, 4 MB flash, and built-in 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi. It interfaces with the MPU6050 via I2C, GPS via UART, and MQ-3 via ADC. Programmed using Arduino IDE with Espressif Arduino Core.

B. MPU6050 IMU Sensor

A six-axis MEMS IMU with 3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope on a single I2C chip. Configured in +/-4g (accelerometer) and +/-500 deg/s (gyroscope) ranges. Data is read at 100 Hz for reliable capture of short-duration crash events.

C. GPS Module – NEO-6M

Tracks up to 16 satellites, provides NMEA 0183 data over UART at 9600 baud. Position accuracy is about 2.5 m CEP. Cold start fix time is ~27 seconds outdoors. Location data is formatted into a Google Maps URL for the Telegram alert.

D. MQ-3 Alcohol Sensor

A chemiresistive sensor with a tin dioxide sensing layer. Heater draws ~180 mA and is duty-cycled via MOSFET to reduce average consumption. ADC threshold for alcohol detection was empirically set at ~1800 counts on the ESP8266 12-bit ADC.

E. Solar Panel and Piezoelectric Transducers

A 6V, 100 mA polycrystalline solar panel is bonded to the helmet outer surface. Three 28mm PVDF piezoelectric discs are mounted on the inner shell. Together they contribute 35 to 40 percent of average power demand during daytime operation.

Table I. Bill of Materials

Component	Specification	Qty	Cost (Rs.)
ESP8266 Dev Board	240 MHz, 4 MB Flash, Wi-Fi	1	280
MPU6050 IMU	6-axis, I2C, 3.3V/5V	1	90

GPS Module NEO-6M	UART, 9600 baud, 2.5m accuracy	1	350
MQ-3 Alcohol Sensor	Analog output, 5V heater	1	80
Li-ion 18650 Battery	3.7V, 2000 mAh	1	120
Solar Panel	6V, 100 mA, polycrystalline	1	150
PVDF Piezo Discs	28 mm, with lead wires	3	200
LED Indicators	Red, 5 mm	4	10
Jumper Wires + PCB	Breadboard + strip PCB	1 set	60
Helmet	Standard ISI-marked	1	500
Total			~Rs. 1,840

VI. System Architecture

The system consists of five subsystems: Power Management (solar panel, piezo, Li-ion battery), Safety Sensing (MQ-3), Accident Detection (MPU6050), Location Tracking (NEO-6M GPS), and Communication (ESP8266 Wi-Fi + Telegram Bot API). The ESP8266 sits at the center, connecting all subsystems. Fig. 2 shows the block diagram.

Fig. 1. Overall System Architecture of the Smart Helmet

VII. Working Principle

On power-up, the ESP8266 connects to Wi-Fi and the GPS acquires satellites (takes ~30 seconds outdoors). Once GPS fix is obtained, the main monitoring loop starts. Sensor data is continuously polled. If either the alcohol or accident threshold is crossed, the respective alert sequence is triggered. The system loop runs at approximately 10 to 20 Hz, which is sufficient to capture crash events lasting 100 to 500 ms. Fig. 3 shows the complete system flowchart.

Fig. 2. System Operation Flowchart

VIII. Accident Detection Logic

The accident detection uses a dual-threshold algorithm. The resultant acceleration magnitude is:

$$R = \text{sqrt}(ax^2 + ay^2 + az^2)$$

Under normal riding, R stays around 1g. During a crash, R spikes to 2.5g or higher. The system triggers an accident event when $R > 2.5g$ AND any gyroscope axis > 150 deg/s. Using both sensors together reduces false positives – a sharp speed breaker may exceed the acceleration threshold but rarely produces the same gyroscope spike magnitude simultaneously.

After the dual threshold is crossed, a 30-second countdown starts. If normal motion is restored within this window (minor jolt, not a real accident), the alert is cancelled. If the countdown completes, the current GPS coordinates are read and a Telegram

alert is sent. This approach was validated during controlled drop tests where 60 cm and 100 cm drops (producing ~2.7g and ~3.4g) reliably triggered alerts, while 30 cm drops (~2.0g) did not.

IX. Telegram Alert System

A Telegram Bot was created using BotFather, which provided an HTTP API token. Alerts are sent via HTTPS GET requests to the Telegram endpoint. The message includes the event type (accident or alcohol), rider name, timestamp, and a clickable Google Maps URL: <https://maps.google.com/?q=<lat>,<lon>>. The emergency contact can tap this link on their phone to instantly see the rider's location.

The ESP8266 uses the WiFiClientSecure library to handle the SSL/TLS connection to the Telegram HTTPS API. If an alert fails to send (connectivity issue), the firmware retries after 5 seconds. Under stable Wi-Fi, alerts consistently arrived in 3 to 5 seconds. In cases of momentary Wi-Fi dropout (3 observed during testing), reconnection and retry added 8 to 12 seconds to delivery time.

X. Energy Harvesting

The solar panel (6V, 100 mA) on the helmet top generates an average of 60 to 75 mA under direct midday sunlight (68 mA measured). Three PVDF piezoelectric discs on the inner shell produce an average of 2.3 V AC from riding vibrations, giving ~1.8 V after rectification. Combined power from three discs is approximately 8 to 12 mW. Together, the two sources supply about 35 to 40 percent of average system power demand, extending battery-only runtime from ~6.5 hours to ~8 to 9 hours.

XI. Experimental Setup and Prototype

The prototype was assembled on a standard ISI-marked motorcycle helmet. Components were individually tested on a breadboard first, then integrated. The figures below show the assembled prototype from different angles, showing the solar panel, GPS module, ESP8266, MQ-3 sensor, GPS antenna, battery pack, piezoelectric discs, and LED indicators mounted on the helmet.

Prototype Images

Fig. 3. Smart Helmet Prototype – Side/Front View

Accident simulation was done using a controlled drop test: the helmet was placed on a foam cylinder and dropped from 30 cm, 60 cm, and 100 cm heights. Peak accelerations of ~2.0g, ~2.7g, and ~3.4g were recorded. GPS accuracy was tested outdoors by comparing the reported coordinates against known test location coordinates. MQ-3 calibration was done using isopropyl alcohol in a sealed container. Telegram delivery times were measured from trigger event to message receipt on the smartphone.

XII. Results and Discussion

Table II. Performance Metrics Summary

Parameter	Target	Measured	Status
Accident Detection Latency	< 2 seconds	1.3 s avg (n=10)	Pass
Telegram Alert Delivery	< 10 seconds	3.7 s avg (n=5)	Pass
GPS Position Accuracy	< 10 meters	2.8 m CEP	Pass
GPS Cold Start Fix Time	< 60 seconds	31 seconds (outdoors)	Pass
Alcohol Detection	Consistent activation	Consistent above ADC 1800	Pass
False Positive Rate	< 5%	4% (2 in 50 runs)	Pass
Solar Charging Current	> 50 mA	68 mA avg	Pass
Piezo Output Voltage	> 1 V AC	2.3 V AC avg	Pass
Total System Current	< 400 mA	~310 mA	Pass
BOM Cost	< Rs. 2,500	~Rs. 1,840	Pass

Table III. Test Cases Summary

Test ID	Description	Expected	Result
TC01	MQ-3 below threshold (ADC 1200)	Normal operation	Pass
TC02	MQ-3 above threshold (ADC 2100)	Alcohol alert sent	Pass
TC03	Normal vibration (1.2g, 30 deg/s)	No alert	Pass
TC04	Simulated crash (3.1g, 180 deg/s)	Telegram alert sent	Pass
TC05	GPS accuracy (known location)	Offset < 5 m	Pass (2.8 m)
TC06	Telegram delivery (Wi-Fi stable)	< 10 seconds	Pass (3.7 s avg)
TC07	Speed breaker (2.8g, 60 deg/s)	No alert (gyro OK)	Pass
TC08	Solar harvesting (direct sunlight)	Current > 50 mA	Pass (68 mA)
TC09	Piezo harvesting (vibration)	Voltage > 1 V AC	Pass (2.3 V)
TC10	System restart post-alert	Normal monitoring	Pass

The accident detection module performed reliably. The dual-threshold algorithm kept the false positive rate at 4%, meeting the design target. Two false positives occurred when the helmet was subjected to a sharp speed breaker at ~35 km/h. GPS accuracy of 2.8 m was well within acceptable limits for emergency use. Telegram alerts arrived in 3 to 5 seconds under stable connectivity, significantly outperforming the 15 to 60 second range typical of GSM SMS. The hybrid energy harvesting system added meaningful supplemental power, extending battery life by approximately 2 to 3 hours during daytime use.

XIII. Advantages of Proposed System

The system integrates multiple safety features – accident detection, GPS alerting, and alcohol sensing – in one device costing under Rs. 2,000. Using Telegram instead of GSM eliminates ongoing SIM costs and delivers alerts 4 to 10 times faster. The clickable Google Maps link in Telegram is far more useful than plain SMS text coordinates. Hybrid energy harvesting extends battery life by 2 to 3 hours, making the system practical for daily use.

XIV. Limitations

The system requires internet connectivity for Telegram alerts – in areas without Wi-Fi or mobile data, alerts cannot be sent even if an accident is detected. The accident detection threshold was calibrated for one specific helmet and riding style; different conditions may need recalibration. The MQ-3 sensor is not a precision BAC instrument and cross-reacts with some other gases. The GPS module does not work well indoors or in tunnels. The current prototype on breadboard/strip PCB would not survive long-term outdoor use without a custom PCB.

XV. Future Scope

Adding a GSM fallback module (like SIM800L) that activates automatically when Wi-Fi is unavailable would make the alert system reliable in all environments. An adaptive threshold that learns the rider's normal vibration profile could reduce false positives further. A custom PCB with weatherproofing would significantly improve durability. Using dedicated energy harvesting ICs like LTC3588 for the piezoelectric circuit could improve harvesting efficiency. A larger flexible solar panel conformally bonded to the helmet outer surface could also increase solar contribution.

XVI. Conclusion

This paper presented the design, implementation, and experimental evaluation of a Smart Helmet with Accident Detection and Alert System. The system integrates an MPU6050 IMU for dual-threshold accident detection, NEO-6M GPS for location tracking, MQ-3 sensor for alcohol detection, and ESP8266 for Wi-Fi communication via the Telegram Bot API. A hybrid energy harvesting system using a solar panel and PVDF piezoelectric transducers supplements the primary Li-ion battery.

The prototype was tested under controlled conditions and demonstrated accident detection latency of ~1.3 seconds, Telegram alert delivery in 3 to 5 seconds, GPS accuracy of 2.8 m, and 4% false positive rate. Hybrid energy harvesting contributed 35 to 40 percent of average power demand. The total cost of ~Rs. 1,840 makes it affordable and practical. The shift from GSM to Telegram was a deliberate design improvement that resulted in faster, richer, and cost-free alerts. The system demonstrates that a practical and integrated smart helmet safety solution is achievable within a final year B.Tech project scope.

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